

Detecting interference between applications and improving the scheduling using malleable application clones*

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel feature for improving the scheduling process based on the performance prediction and the detection of CPU and I/O interference between applications. This feature consists of using malleable synthetic benchmarks -called clones- that reproduce the behaviour of applications executed in a cluster. These proxies can be used with two objectives: to build large and representative datasets that can be used to train the machine learning algorithms for modelling the platform workload, and to evaluate in advance if two executing applications can potentially produce contention hazards related to the shared use of the system resources like CPU, cache memory or I/O bandwidth. The proposed framework generates application clones based on generic-purpose performance information collected from monitoring. Unlike other works based on the use of micro-architectures or metrics obtained from simulators, in the approach presented in this work the application clones generate similar behaviour without extracting data from the binaries, avoiding the necessity of managing code or data from the applications. One advantage of this approach is that they can be shared securely because they have not been generated using any piece of the original code. In addition, the proposed clones are malleable, so they are also able to model the application behaviour under a different number of processes. In this work, we show how the use of clones contributes to improving the application scheduling by reducing the number of evaluations that is necessary to perform, and to detect performance degradation (interference) without the necessity of involving the execution of the actual applications. We evaluate the proposed clone generation approach on two sets of benchmarks (CPU and I/O oriented) and several applications. We also compare the performance

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obtained during the execution of the proxies and the applications to show their similarity. Finally, we include an evaluation of the interference detection using this novel approach.

application clones, malleability, performance modelling, interference detection, application scheduling

1 Introduction

The use of benchmarks is one of the key procedures to assess computer systems. Researchers and engineers need to quantify the performance of their applications by running them under different conditions and in different architecture configurations. Some uses of those benchmarks are to compare the design alternatives during development, test computer systems for guiding the development or enable a fair evaluation of the performance in different architectures. Examples of well-known benchmark suites are SPEC, CPU2006, ImplanBench and PARSEC. These benchmarks permit evaluating the performance of general-purpose processors and represent standard benchmarks that are mostly generated based on open-source programs. Their main limitation is that they are not always representative of real-world applications, and usually, they are different from the applications of interest to the developers and researchers. One alternative consists of using real applications. This permits the industry to improve the computer systems based on the application characteristics that are going to be most frequently executed on the platform. On the other hand, researchers also benefit from the industry because they gain access to better design solutions to their problems. The main problem of this alternative is that the application code may be proprietary and could not be available for testing and that its installation and setup may require a high effort.

This work combines system and application monitoring to provide a scheme that permits modelling the applications. The goal is to generate application clones -also called micro-benchmarks- that can be used as benchmarks to reproduce the application behaviour (CPU, memory, network and I/O usage). In this context, this paper presents a new alternative for application clones creation based on the generic performance information obtained by the LIMITLESS system monitor. The monitor collects the performance metrics during the execution of a certain application. Then, the analytic component processes those metrics to generate a malleable clone that reproduces the same performance metrics and can be reconfigured at runtime. Malleability is implemented by means of the FlexMPI FlexMPIEuropar runtime.

The proposed application clone generation and use have three key features: (1) no information is revealed about the proprietary application, (2) the performance metrics related to the clones are similar to the original application so that the clones can be used as a benchmark that has the same behaviour as the original application, and (3) they can be used in combination with an intelligent scheduler (they have mechanisms to analyze and exploit the collected information to improve the scheduling task) to evaluate and avoid the potential risk of

interference hazards between different applications. We define an interference hazard as a situation when two running applications compete for the system resources and create a contention that reduces the application performance.

The use of clones permits implementing more complex scheduling techniques in which different non-conflicting applications can be executed in the same compute nodes, reducing the number of executing nodes and saving energy. As far as we know, this is the first work that uses malleable application clones. This can be used for taking advantage of the unused resources in large-scale systems. These resources (compute nodes, existing network and I/O bandwidth, etc.) are typically available because the system utilization does not reach 100%.

The main contributions of this work are:

- An application clone generation approach that provides synthetic malleable micro-benchmarks.
- The introduction of malleable capabilities in the clones for dynamically evaluating different number of processes, and reproducing different levels of data redistribution between the processes.
- A new application scheduling methodology based on machine learning algorithms and proxies that permits to identify interference in advance.

2 Monitor architecture

Figure 1: General overview of the system architecture and interrelation with other components.

LIMITLESS¹ is a lightweight and scalable monitor that operates on each compute node and provides information about available system resources and the

¹<https://gitlab.arcos.inf.uc3m.es/acascajo/limitless-monitor>

performance of the applications that are being executed. Figure 1 shows a general overview of the LIMITLESS architecture. It integrates other components like the application scheduler, FlexMPI and CLARISSE runtimes. FlexMPI provides malleability at a process level, and CLARISSE decouples the policy, control, and data layers of the I/O stack software in order to simplify the task of globally coordinating the parallel I/O on large-scale HPC platforms. The framework includes four main modules: a *System monitor* that collects the performance metrics from the cluster, an *ElasticSearch* database gormley2015elasticsearch that provides persistent storage, Kibana, a *GUI* for displaying the cluster information in a user-friendly format, and the LIMITLESS *Analytic* component (LAN) that analyses and models the executing applications. This component provides storage, visualization, communication with the scheduler, and is responsible for the application performance prediction. It stores and manages the application models, generates the predictors, trains and executes the machine learning algorithms, and configures the malleable application clones. The application clones generation is implemented in a separated component that requires communication with the scheduler and the LAN component.

Figure 1 illustrates the system data flow. When one application is executed, the scheduler notifies the LAN component about the application characteristics (which is used to identify and classify the application). After that, when the applications are executed two different metrics are collected simultaneously: at node level to the monitor and application level to FlexMPI and CLARISSE. The collected metrics include general information such as the machine configuration (number of CPUs, cores, network interfaces, I/O interfaces, main memory, etc.) and the current usage (CPU usage, memory in use, I/O (read and write) and network (send and receive) bandwidth, energy consumed, cache hits and misses, etc.), and all of them are collected periodically by the LDM. Then, both metrics are processed by the respective runtimes and are written into ElasticSearch. After that, LAN creates an application model using the information stored in ElasticSearch. Once the application model is generated, the LAN also creates the application clone associated with it, which can be used to generate more performance metrics to increase the size of the dataset. Finally, the prediction model is sent to LIMITLESS to predict the performance of the applications on each node. During all these processes, Kibana may be used to visualize the cluster status. The following sections provide a more detailed description of these components.

2.1 System monitor

The monitor is designed to provide performance information of the nodes and applications in large-scale systems. The monitoring interval -time between consecutive collected metrics- can be set in a range of time from hours to sub-seconds. In addition, this period can be modified online without the necessity of restarting the system or the monitor and it is possible to use a different one for each node. The monitor overhead in the compute nodes is low (less

than 1% on CPU consumption and a memory footprint of 3890 KB in resident memory (cascajo2021) CASCAJO2022104586, which means that the monitoring has a minimal impact on the applications that are being executed in the same compute nodes.

The system monitor consists of one *LIMITLESS DaeMon Monitor* (LDM) per node, which periodically collects the performance metrics; a set of *LIMITLESS DaeMon Aggregators* (LDAs), that forwards the information from the LDMs to other aggregators or servers; and the *LIMITLESS DaeMon Server* (LDS) that gathers and stores the monitoring information in ElasticSearch. The deployment over the architecture is done hierarchically, generating a data flow from the nodes (LDMs) to the main server (LDS) and the database. The connection topology between the components can be user-defined and be mapped to the existing cluster topology. For instance, one LDS per rack and one LDM per node (note that a server node can also run a LDM process).

3 Building synthetic micro-benchmarks: application clones

There are three application scheduling strategies implemented in the framework. The first alternative was implemented in cascajo2019performance and uses the monitoring information to make decisions about the application schedule depending on the available resources, the application performance and other user-defined metrics. The idea is to map (if possible) two different applications to shared compute nodes in order to maximize the system resource utilization. This is only applied if the applications do not produce interference, i.e. their performance is not degraded under resource sharing.

The second alternative was implemented in cascajo2021 and uses the generated application models to predict the future performance of the applications in order to support the decision-making process related to the application scheduling. This alternative does not produce good results if the accuracy of the predictor is poor. The third strategy presented in this work overcomes the previous problem by using the application clones. The idea now is to combine the execution of the clones with other applications in order to identify, in a more accurate way, the sets of applications that can run concurrently in the same compute nodes without creating interference hazards. The proposed methodology to generate application clones is shown in Figure 2. The first step is the application characterization which consists of collecting the performance metrics associated with the running applications. The *LIMITLESS Monitor* is in charge of providing these metrics that include, among others, the CPU and memory usage, I/O writes per monitoring period for every I/O device, network bandwidth used on every network interface, etc. The second step consists of storing the performance metrics associated with each application in the ElasticSearch database. Using this information, the analytic component generates a model of each application that capture its main features. Finally, the last step

Figure 2: Designed methodology to create the application clones based on the monitoring data, and how that new data is used to produce more accurate predictors.

is to generate the application clone based on the previous model, resulting in an executable that reproduces the application behaviour, i.e, generates a temporal sequence of the same performance metrics as the original application.

Note that a certain application executed with different input configurations may have different behaviours. In this case, in order to produce different models related to each case, it is desirable to analyse each configuration independently. Note that these situations can be detected using the *application context* (command line and input parameters, provided from the scheduler to the LAN component) for classifying the application models. All the traces belonging to the same context are stored together and used to generate the same model. The set of application executions belonging to the same context is called *application ensemble*. Each ensemble has related a certain model. In this way, if the application is executed in a new context (for instance, changing the input parameters) it will be related to a new ensemble and a different model will be generated.

The LAN component uses the performance models to generate the application clones. These clones are configured as a template of a parallel program written in C, parallelized with the MPI library and enhanced with malleable capabilities with FlexMPI. The clones contain different parameters that determine the duration of the CPU, communication and I/O phases as well as the file access pattern and data distribution scheme among the existing processes.

All the collected metrics are general performance counters and do not include specific counters related to the application's internal parallelism or patterns (for instance, different numbers of threads used by OpenMP in different scopes). It means that the application behaviour could change. However, as the clones reproduce the performance levels indicated by the collected metrics by the monitor, if any change is detected in those metrics, the clone is supposed to reproduce it as well. Besides, if that change in the performance is related to different parameters (application context), the system will create a new model

and clone.

3.1 Use of clones for application performance modelling

Deep-learning networks are used to perform automatic feature extraction from multiple sources of input data. The most traditional machine-learning algorithms need to analyze large amounts of data in order to provide accurate predictions, and those datasets have to be representative enough of the features that the users want to extract. In the context of application performance modelling, the training datasets are obtained from executing the application multiple times. The more data a network can be trained on, the more accurate the prediction is likely to be. Note that we assume that a certain training dataset is related to the same application ensemble, so ideally all the application runs would produce the same traces because both the binary and application inputs are the same in all the runs. However, when the application is executed on real platforms it is subjected to variability introduced by the interaction between the application and all the levels of the system architecture (cache, virtual memory, I/O and network buffering, etc.) that introduces changes in the application monitoring traces. This is why it is necessary to have multiple application runs in order to consider all the possible variations in the traces and accurately model the application behaviour.

Following this idea, LIMITLESS uses the application clones to generate more data when the system workload is reduced. Each execution of the clone is stored as a model of the original application, increasing the dataset for that application. Finally, this dataset is used by the prediction algorithms to model its performance. This process avoids involving the user in the application execution because clones are executed by the framework instead of the users and neither the original program nor its related input data is needed. On the other hand, the clones are also subjected to the variability depicted before, because they also perform CPU, memory, network and I/O operations. In addition, the malleable clones permit to dynamically change the number of processes. In this way, the use of clones permits generating multiple application datasets in a dynamic and simple way. In the context of a real platform, the clones enrich the scheduler with additional information to predict possible future states of the nodes and applications. Currently, this information is used to perform dynamic application scheduling based on predicting the future states of the cluster.

Regarding the algorithms used, we can separate them into two groups: neural networks and machine learning. Neural networks perform forecasting, while machine learning characterizes and classifies the applications. Some of these algorithms have been described in previous articles already, but in this work, we have implemented new mechanisms for modelling and predicting the application performance. The new methodology combines two algorithms, one from each group: we use a neural network for forecasting the application performance and a machine learning regression model to refine the predictions provided by the neural network.

In order to have a precise model using neural networks for forecasting, it

is necessary to know which features are more suitable to be acquired by the learning algorithm. The following concepts are used to define the most common characteristics of these features:

- Trend: time-series show a trend when the value variably changes with time. A positive trend means the values of a time-window increase, and a negative trend the opposite.
- Seasonality: this refers to a property of time series that exhibit periodical patterns repeating at a certain frequency.
- Cycles: time-series that includes repeated trends every certain time.
- Stationarity: time-series that show statistical features that do not change over time.
- Residual: Once the trend and seasonality have been extracted, what remains is the residual (error related to the model).

The employed algorithms are able to learn and generalize features such as trends, cycles, seasonality and stationarity data. However, a problem arises when the time series includes a high percentage of residuals. This feature is the hardest, sometimes impossible, to model. To cope with it, we model these residuals using a machine learning regression model, which can be configured to be more or less reactive to these residuals. Due to this, it is possible to model and predict the application behaviour, even when the applications have different performance models. For instance, when the application shows repeated patterns or trends and when the application behaviour exhibits performance bursts with different magnitudes and frequencies.

3.2 Use of clones for application interference analysis

One of the main objectives to generate these application clones is the interference evaluation when two applications are running and sharing resources. Note that in general, for a certain application only the last allocated node could have available resources to share with other applications. For example, if *App1* requires 28 processes and *App2* 8 in a cluster with nodes with 24 cores each. The scheduler will allocate 24 processes in the first node and the other 4 processes in the second node for *App1*. In case of sharing the resources, the scheduler will allocate *App2* the second compute node. In this case, only two compute nodes (instead of three) will be involved in the application execution.

However, interference may arise when different applications are running in the same compute nodes (CPU, memory or I/O contention at compute nodes) or when they are executed in different compute nodes but are performing I/O at the same time (I/O contention at storage nodes). In this way, one interference situation may occur when the scheduler allocates the jobs in non-exclusive nodes in order to perform a better utilization of the resources. With this configuration, depending on the available resources of a certain compute node, another

application can share the unused ones. However, there is a potential risk of interference between them. To improve the scheduling task, we propose the use of malleable application clones to generate a *profiling study* under different workloads while real applications are running in the system.

In order to determine if there is interference between two different jobs (two applications, an application and a clone, or two clones), the system collects the performance metrics from the applications when they are running in exclusive compute nodes. Then, when another application is allocated in the same compute node the same performance metrics are collected. By comparing the *exclusively-collected* and the *shared-collected* metrics, the system is able to identify if there is performance degradation. Using this information, the scheduler can make decisions about the scheduling Ekanadham1995 cascajo2019performance 8821052 SINGH201921 10.1145/3392717.3392764 cascajo2021 CASCAJO2022104586, for instance migrating one of them to avoid the interference, or evaluating if that interference is mitigated when the number of processes is increased or decreased for one of them.

3.2.1 CPU-related interference.

In order to analyse the CPU interference, the collected information results in three performance counters: **RTIME** indicates the CPU time per group of iterations, **CTIME** is the communication time per group of iterations, and the execution time **TIME**. The execution time indicates if there is any kind of interference between two applications: if the execution time of an application is lower than that obtained when another application is running in the same node, it means that the second application is interfering with the first one. However, using the other counters, the system can identify more details about the reasons behind the performance degradation.

Note that CPU contention can be related to the shared access to the cache memory or the multiple executions of different application instructions. When the interference is related to CPU contention, the second application could reduce its processes to mitigate it, or the scheduler could move the second application to another compute node, where the application could share the resources with another application or could be run in an exclusive node. FlexMPI performs these operations of expanding, reducing and migrating. It allows the application to increase or decrease its processes and redistribute the data every reconfiguration. Note that the job is dynamically reconfigured instead of being terminated and restarted with a new configuration.

3.2.2 I/O-related interference.

In order to analyse the I/O interference, the collected information results in other three different measurements: **IOTIME**, **IOREADS** and **IOWRITES**. The first metric measures the time spent in I/O operations during a certain time interval. The second and the third counters provide extra information by collecting the number of reads/writes each second. In this way, the **IOTIME** counter permits

to determine whether the I/O time increases when two applications are running concurrently, thus there is a risk of the existence of I/O interference between them. In addition, the other two metrics quantitatively determine the degree of interference.

Efficient balancing of computational and I/O resources is one of the existing challenges in the HPC infrastructures panziera2017strategic. This balance depends on different factors, such as the interaction between the hardware components, the software stack and the performed operations by the applications SINGH201921. All of these factors may interfere with the I/O producing performance variations. It is a challenge to detect and avoid interference due to the dynamic nature of the HPC platforms and applications. In this context, malleable application clones are employed during the execution of the real application for evaluating the degree of potential I/O interference between them. The objective is to evaluate different configurations to generate a scalability model that could support the scheduler with the scheduling making decisions. Clones leverage malleability to be executed with a different number of processes (note that this number can be dynamically adjusted), and this malleability relies on FlexMPI for dynamically creating or destroying processes and automatically redistributing or replicating the data.

Besides, the malleable clones for I/O include a parameter called replication factor (RF) that models how the data is distributed when the number of the application processes increases.

4 Evaluation

The evaluation has been divided into four sections. The first one shows the results of the CPU-related clones, including a comparison between the original benchmark and the clone based on it. The original benchmarks used come from the Princeton Application Repository for Shared-Memory Computers (PARSEC) parsec, which is a benchmark suite composed of multi-threaded programs that are focused on emerging workloads, and NASA Advanced Supercomputing (NAS) Parallel Benchmarks (NPB) npb, which consists of a small set of applications designed to evaluate the performance of parallel supercomputers.

The second section shows the results of the I/O-related clones. In this case, the applications have been selected from a set of HPC applications that are previously used in some related works, and it includes the Hardware Accelerated Cosmology Code (HACC), a dataset for scientific deep learning that includes pre-trained networks to simulate inertial confinement fusion use cases (JAG), a classical molecular dynamics code (LAMMPS), and the principal computational kernel that is pertinent to Nek5000 nek5000 (Nekbone).

The third section consists of an evaluation of the predictors when LIMITLESS uses the proxies to train the algorithms instead of the original applications. Finally, the last section corresponds to the interference evaluation by using the application clones. Both the scalability of the applications and the interference produced between them are analyzed. The experiments have been done in a

physical platform that consists of eight compute nodes. One partition of the cluster contains six nodes with Intel(R) Xeon(R) E7 with 12 cores and 128GB of RAM. The second partition contains two nodes with Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6212U CPU @ 2.40GHz with 24 cores and 315GB of RAM. The connection between nodes is a 10 Gbps Ethernet. The I/O is based on Lustre file system. All experiments have been performed using all available nodes. However, the figures shown in this section show the performance counters on individual nodes.

4.1 CPU application clone modelling

The different benchmarks used for the CPU evaluation include, as we have indicated before, a set of applications from PARSEC, NPB and the Jacobi method. More specifically, the considered benchmarks are:

- Jacobi: is an algorithm for determining the solutions of a diagonally dominant system of linear equations. Each diagonal element is solved for, and an approximate value is obtained. The process is then iterated until it converges.
- Integer-Sort: is a kernel that performs random memory access. It belongs to the class of bucket sort algorithms which perform an all-to-all communication pattern (by means of the OpenMP library).
- Multi-grid: solves a 3D Poisson equation using a V-cycle multigrid method. It exhibits structured and long-range communications.
- Bodytrack: tracks a human body with multiple cameras through an image sequence.
- Blacksholes: calculates the prices for a portfolio of European options analytically with the Black-Scholes partial differential equation (PDE) parsecwiki.

For each figure in this section, the x-axis represents the execution time in seconds while the y-axis represents the usage percentage. Note that every figure follows the same colour scheme for CPU (orange), memory (blue) and network (grey) usage. These performance metrics have been obtained from the LIMITLESS monitor (see section 2.1).

Figure 3 shows the performance behaviour of the Jacobi method. It exhibits characteristic CPU, memory and communication patterns. The CPU phases are correlated to the memory and the communication phases. Once LIMITLESS has modelled the application, the LAN component generates its clone, which produces the performance behaviour that can be seen in Figure 4.

The next two charts (Figures 6 and 7 show the performance behaviour of Integer-sort (IS) and Multi-grid (MG) benchmarks from the NAS Parallel Benchmarks. For the Integer-sort benchmark, the program performs a series of computations, including a gradual increase in memory usage until all data is loaded in memory (the first 30 seconds of the execution). Figure 7 illustrates

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Figure 3: Jacobi I/O (JIO) executing with six parallel processes.

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Figure 4: Jacobi I/O (JIO) clone executing with six parallel processes.

Figure 5: Jacobi I/O model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the usage percentage.

the performance behaviour obtained from the clone execution. In this case, the CPU usage is a bit higher than the original due to the overhead of the memory replication.

Figure 9 shows the performance behaviour of the Multi-Grid benchmark (MG). This use case is similar to the last one (and similar to the rest of the benchmarks of the NPB 1). MG also performs a series of computations keeping the CPU and the memory mostly constant along the execution time. Figure 10 corresponds to the performance behaviour obtained from the clone execution.

Figures 12 and 13 show the performance behaviour of Bodytrack. The first one corresponds to a computer vision workload, which performs medium working sets of computation. It represents an example of a pattern with cycles that consist of seventeen computation phases that are well replicated by the clone in the second figure. There are no significant changes in the memory consumption, and it keeps mostly constant along the execution time. The performance of the last use case can be seen in Figure 15, which corresponds to the Blackscholes benchmark. It performs a unique computation (but longer) phase in the middle of the executions. At the end of the execution, there is a peak of communication. The performance metrics obtained from the clone execution can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 6: Integer-Sort (IS) executing with 12 parallel processes.

Figure 7: Integer-Sort (IS) clone executing with 12 parallel processes.

Figure 8: Integer-Sort model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the usage percentage.

According to our experiments, in all the cases the clone program is able to reproduce the original workload, despite the fact of existing small differences between the original program and the clone. It is due to LIMITLESS does not perform deep profiling of the applications to generate 100% accurate proxies. Instead of that, LIMITLESS builds generic proxies that reproduce, with certain accuracy, the performance behaviour, the computation phases, the memory consumption and the network traffic. Note that the clones are subsequently used to generate new data to refine the performance predictors. It is important to highlight that the predictors are re-built every time a new model is stored in the LIMITLESS database, so the clone programs improve their accuracy over time.

4.2 I/O application clone modelling

The different benchmarks used for the I/O evaluation include programs with multiple degrees of I/O patterns:

- HACC-IO and HACC-MK: Hardware Accelerated Cosmology Code. The HACC framework uses the N-body paradigm to simulate the formation of structure in fluids under the influence of gravity in the universe. We evaluate two implementations of this benchmark related to CPU and I/O operations.

Figure 9: Multi-Grid (MG) executing with 12 parallel processes.

Figure 10: Multi-Grid (MG) clone executing with 12 parallel processes.

Figure 11: Multi-Grid model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the usage percentage.

- JAG: is a set of pre-trained machine learning models, architectures and implementations for building surrogate models in scientific machine learning. Most of them have been outlined in the Department of Energy’s recent report on [osti1478744.LAMMPS : isamoleculardynamicsapplication.Itisabletomodeldifferentsystems\(state, etc.\)usingavarietyof force fields and boundary conditions.](#)
- Nekbone: It solves a standard Poisson equation using the spectral element method with an iterative conjugate gradient solver with a basic preconditioner. It captures the basic structure and user interface of the extensive Nek5000 software, which is a high-order, incompressible Navier-Stokes solver.

This section is focused on I/O performance². To provide accurate application clones regarding the I/O, we have implemented a new algorithm to combine a forecasting neural network and a machine learning regression model. Different from other metrics (such as CPU and Memory consumption), I/O has more variability because multiple factors may degrade the read and write performance. Examples of them are the I/O interference with other running applications or the use of a poor I/O locality access pattern. The neural network used in this

²The proposed clones can reproduce both read and write patterns. However, due to the space limits, this section shows only write patterns.

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Figure 12: Bodytrack (BT) executing with 12 parallel processes.

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Figure 13: Bodytrack (BT) clone executing with 12 parallel processes.

Figure 14: Bodytrack model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the usage percentage.

work can generalize the I/O behaviour of the applications, but the I/O intensive phases are difficult to model by the network due to the performance peaks they produce. We combine this network with a regression model, which can deal with these peaks, to achieve good accuracy.

Figure 18 shows the I/O writes behaviour of the HACC-IO application. It exhibits cyclic phases with a negative trend for each one. The writes are more intensive when the simulation generates the N-bodies, and the intensity decreases with the number of bodies moving. Figure 19 shows the I/O writes generated by the application clone in the same node, device and file system.

Figure 21 shows the I/O writes behaviour of the HACC-MK application. As HACC-MK is focused on the computation, in this case, the I/O phases correspond to the performed checkpointing at the end of one simulation iteration. There are minor write operations during the execution, but the two peaks (around second 860 and 1760) identify the checkpointing phase. There are no trends or seasonality in the data. Figure 22 shows the I/O writes generated by the application clone.

Figure 24 shows the I/O writes behaviour of the JAG application. In this figure, we can see that there are periodic phases of I/O with different intensities. There are no clear trends or seasonality, but signs of a cycle in the access pattern. Figure 25 shows the I/O writes generated by the application clone.

Figure 15: Blackscholes (BS) executing with 12 parallel processes.

Figure 16: Blackscholes (BS) clone executing with 12 parallel processes.

Figure 17: Blackscholes model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the usage percentage.

Figure 27 shows the I/O writes behaviour of the LAMMPS application. Like in the previous use case, we can observe that there are periodical phases of I/O with different intensities, but these are more sparse. There are no clear trends or seasonality, but signs of a repeating pattern in the I/O. Figure 28 shows the I/O writes generated by the application clone.

Figure 30 shows the I/O writes behaviour of the Nekbone application. This application is continuously performing I/O, but four I/O bursts can be observed in this figure. These bursts can be identified as seasons or cycles. Figure 31 shows the I/O writes generated by the application clone. Based on these experiments we can observe that the clones are able to reproduce diverse application I/O patterns.

As part of the evaluation, we also modelled the relationship between the application data distribution and the I/O traffic. For instance, if one application uses partitions of its arrays of data and duplicates the number of processes, each new one will receive half of the data previously assigned to the previous processes, so the overall I/O traffic will approximately remain the same (the difference will be the number of processes involved in the I/O operation). Examples of these applications are numerical kernels, based on sparse or dense matrices. In contrast, if the application does not use partitioned data, every process will receive a replication of the original data. In this case, the data allo-

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Figure 18: HACC-IO writes during the execution.

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Figure 19: HACC-IO clone writes during the execution.

Figure 20: HACC-IO model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the KB written each second.

cation will linearly increase with the number of processes. In this case, the I/O traffic is expected to increase as well with the number of processes. Examples are simulators that compute different scenarios based on the same input data.

We also consider intermediate cases in which there is a partial level of replication (for instance, applications in which the boundaries of the problem are replicated). In the model, the Replication Factor (RF) can be a value between 0.0 and 1.0. RF=0.0 means that there is a 100% of overlap between the processes (each one computes 100% of the data). RF=1.0 indicates no overlaps (the data is partitioned equally for each process). Note that at the end of the data redistribution phase the replication factor directly drops on the I/O traffic by changing the volume of data that is written.

Figures 33, 34, 35, 36 and 37 show the different application clones with 2 and 4 dynamic (created using malleability) processes. The left and right columns show the execution for two and four processes, respectively. The X-axis represents the execution time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the KB of data written per second. The first row corresponds to an RF=0.0, the second one to RF=0.5, and the last one to RF=1.0. We can observe that the I/O traffic is strongly dependent of the replication factor.

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Figure 21: HACC-MK writes during the execution.

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Figure 22: Clone 2. HACC-MK clone writes during the execution.

Figure 23: HACC-MK model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the KB written each second.

N. procs	Expand/shrink	Data redistrib.
8 to 12	0.891120	0.121103
12 to 14	0.949042	0.116333
14 to 16	0.898925	0.114143
16 to 18	0.901130	0.120974
18 to 20	0.908145	0.114886
20 to 24	0.909972	0.104716
24 to 28	0.907456	0.104094
28 to 8	0.017645	0.131265
Overhead	6.383435	0.927514

Table 1: Jacobi use case - Interference evaluation using malleability with one clone, from 8 processes to 28. The table shows the seconds spent on expanding/shrinking the processes, and the time spent on redistributing the data.

4.3 Use of application clones for application scheduling

In this section, we show how the clones can be used to replace the actual applications in the context of application interference analysis. As the clones offer similar results for CPU, I/O, memory and communication patterns, the idea is that once a certain application is modelled and its related clone is created, then the scheduler is able to use the clone to evaluate the application performance

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Figure 24: JAG writes during the execution.

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Figure 25: JAG clone writes during the execution.

Figure 26: JAG model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the KB written each second.

N. procs	Expand/shrink	Data redistrib.
8 to 12	0.087823	0.125488
12 to 14	0.088597	0.105049
14 to 16	0.935568	0.115070
16 to 8	0.002273	0.158980
Total overhead	1.111978 s.	0.5048587 s.

Table 2: Gradient use case - Overhead using malleability with one clone, from 8 processes to 16. The table shows the seconds spent on expanding/shrinking the processes, and the time spent on redistributing the data.

and the interference degree under different conditions (number of processes and different degrees of replication factors). The obtained information will support the scheduler in the decision-making process.

This section is divided into two subsections. The first one shows examples of CPU interference analysis using malleable clones. The second one shows a similar study but focused on the I/O.

4.3.1 CPU interference analysis

With this analysis the scheduler is able to make more precise decisions for future executions, knowing which applications can share a node without producing

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Figure 27: LAMMPS writes during the execution.

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Figure 28: LAMMPS clone during the execution.

Figure 29: LAMMPS model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the KB written each second.

interference (thus degrading their performance). The first use case corresponds to the Jacobi application. Figure 38 shows the execution time of the Jacobi use case when it is executed with a changing degree of interference. In the baseline case (called Orig) Jacobi is exclusively executed (without any other application) using 12 processes. Then, the blue bars show the execution time of the original Jacobi instance (using 12 processes) when another Jacobi instance is simultaneously running in the same compute node with a range from 8 to 28 processes. Note that the execution time of the second instance is not included in the graphic. We can observe that the simultaneous execution of two applications degrades the performance of the first one (the original one). The interference reaches the maximum value with 12 processes in the second application. This is because all the cores are in use, and both instances are carrying out the same CPU, cache and memory operations. The orange bar shows the execution time of the original Jacobi instance (that is the same as the previous case) when the clone is simultaneously running in the same compute node. In other words, now the second Jacobi program is replaced by its related clone. We evaluate again the interference for a range from 8 to 28 processes per clone (the original Jacobi code is always executed with 12 processes). We can observe that the degree of degradation produced by the clone is similar to the one caused by the original Jacobi application.

The second use case corresponds to the Conjugate Gradient algorithm. The same scenario is proposed in Figure 39: first, the original application is ex-

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Figure 30: Nekbone writes during the execution.

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Figure 31: Nekbone clone writes during the execution.

Figure 32: Nekbone model. The X-axis represents the time in seconds while the Y-axis represents the KB written each second.

Figure 33: HACCIO replication factor analysis. The left column shows the two-processes use cases, and the right column the four-processes use cases. The first row corresponds a RF=0.0, the second one to RF=0.5, and the last one RF=1.0.

clusively executed with 12 processes and then is run with another application (Conjugate Gradient) or its related clone. The number of processes for the second application now ranges between 8 and 16 processes due to the problem

Figure 34: HACCMK replication factor analysis.

Figure 35: JAG replication factor analysis.

size limitation. We can observe the same behaviour as in the previous cases, producing maximum interference with 12 processes. The interference produced by the real application and the clone is similar in all cases.

Another advantage of using malleable clones is that it permits to carry out a whole range of evaluations during a single clone execution. This means that it is possible to execute one instance of the Jacobi or Gradient clone and dynamically increase or reduce the number of processes for evaluating a changing range of parallelism and data distribution degrees. The results of the dynamic clone reconfiguration are shown in Tables 1 and 2 that summarize the overheads of performing dynamic reconfiguration of the Jacobi and Conjugate gradient clones. Tables include the related overhead for creating and destroying the

Figure 36: LAMMPS replication factor analysis.

Figure 37: Nekbone replication factor analysis.

processes and redistributing the data. Note that these overheads are much smaller than the application execution time.

When comparing the required time to evaluate interference with two applications, we can assume that the second application has to be executed multiple times, increasing the overall evaluation time. In our examples, it would take $32,734s$ for the first use case and $44,868s$ for the second one. Note that here the second application has to be run multiple and independent numbers of times with a changing number of processes. When clones are used instead, it is possible to evaluate the interference with a single clone run, changing the processes dynamically. The clone is now not related to the user, but to the runtime, that can dynamically execute it for certain time until the performance evaluation

Figure 38: Use case Jacobi - Comparison between the execution time of Jacobi instances running concurrently in the same compute node and the same executions using proxies. The interference is directly related to the execution time.

Figure 39: Use case Gradient - Comparison between the execution time of Conjugate Gradient instances running concurrently in the same compute node and the same executions using proxies. The interference is directly related to the execution time.

is completed and then, dynamically change the number of process to continue the evaluation under a different configuration. In this case, the time needed is reduced to *3850s* for the first use case, and *6003s* for the second one. These times include the complete evaluation for multiple number of processes.

4.3.2 I/O interference analysis

In this section, we analyze the I/O interference between HACC-IO and Jacobi-IO applications that are executed with 4 and 6 processes, respectively. Figures 40 and 41 show the original application I/O access pattern when they are executed exclusively, i.e. without interference. Figures 43 and 46 show the interference produced by the concurrent execution of both applications. And finally, figures 44 and 47 show the interference produced by the concurrent execution of both application clones. Note that now the overall execution time is larger, as it can be seen in Table 3. Figures 49 and 50 quantifies the interference gen-

erated between both applications and clones. The use of clones degrades the application performance, but in a higher extent than using the original one.

I/O time	Original	Orig. interf.	Clone interf.
HACC-IO	1962s	2568s	2634s
Jacobi-IO	133s	155s	177s

Table 3: I/O time related to HACC-IO and Jacobi-I/O applications.

LIMITLESS framework includes mechanisms for avoiding CPU and I/O interference once it is detected. However, these solutions are reacting mechanisms instead of preventing mechanisms. The idea behind this work is to use the malleable clones to anticipate the interference analysis in order to determine in advance if two applications will produce I/O contention. Once a potential interference situation is detected, then the scheduler can make decisions to mitigate or avoid it. Examples of these decisions are migrating one application to another node that has a different related I/O node, changing the configuration of the burst buffers or increasing or reducing the number of processes for modifying the application I/O bandwidth 10.1145/3392717.3392764. All these topics are out of the scope of this work. Note that according to the results of the interference analysis, it is possible to dynamically evaluate different I/O interference scenarios with a changing number of processes and I/O patterns. This permits to make different decisions related to the application and I/O scheduling. These decisions include executing different non-conflicting applications in the same compute nodes for sharing the resources, reducing the overall number of allocated resources, and avoiding I/O interference between different applications.

5 Related work

In this section, we introduce some related publications that are relevant in the fields of monitoring, application cloning and application scheduling. Unfortunately, it does not contains any related work about malleable clones, because, as far as we know, our proposal is a novelty.

The main goal of LukRobert is to provide easy-to-use, portable, transparent, and efficient instrumentation tools (called Pintools) that are written in C/C++ using Pin’s rich API. They provide different instrumentation than other similar tools, for example, Valgrind and dynamRIO. The instrumentation does not interfere with the loads/stores in the registers. The authors provide a comparison between PIN, Valgrind and dinamRIO, where we can observe that PIN and dinamRIO outperform Valgrind without instrumentation, and PIN outperforms both Valgrind and dinamRIO when we consider performance with instrumentation.

In Ganesan2010 the authors proposed a synthetic benchmark generation to (1) reduce the simulation time employing these proxies generated instead of the

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Figure 40: HACC-IO - writing pattern in exclusive nodes.

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Figure 41: Jacobi I/O - writing pattern in exclusive nodes.

Figure 42: I/O writing patterns related to original HACC-IO and Jacobi I/O executions while running separately in exclusive nodes.

original applications, and (2) share these proxies for computer architects, as some of the specific target applications are proprietary, and vendors hesitate to share them. They provided the synthetic clones for CPU2006 and ImplanBench workloads. The metrics used include the Memory Level Parallelism (MLP) of those workloads to estimate the burstiness of accesses to the main memory, and the features needed to characterize a benchmark are: a Statistical Flow Graph (SFG) that is used to capture the control flow behaviour; a branch prediction algorithm based on the branch transition rate; the Instruction Level Parallelism (ILP) in the workload; and the memory access pattern. Instead of capturing data to get the memory access pattern, the authors used a stride base memory access (because Joshi et al. concluded previously in Joshi that most of the load and store instructions in CPU200 workloads have that pattern).

Later, in Ganesan2014, the authors proposed a framework that can generate application clones for real-world multi-threaded applications based on: shared caches, coherence logic, out-of-order cores, interconnection network and DRAM. This framework is evaluated by generating clones from the PARSEC benchmark suite and comparing their results in terms of performance. Their solution consists of extracting performance information from the applications and then generating the code for the clones based on a C template with some options. The main benefit of creating and using these clones is that they have

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Figure 43: HACC-IO clone: writing pattern while running concurrently with Jacobi I/O in shared nodes.

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Figure 44: HACC-IO original: writing pattern while running concurrently with Jacobi I/O in shared nodes.

Figure 45: I/O writing patterns related to the clone and original HACC-IO executions respectively while running concurrently with Jacobi I/O in shared nodes.

used a simulator to calculate the energy consumption of different workloads and different parameters, and the simulations are four magnitude orders faster using the clones due to the number of instructions executed (millions versus thousands of instructions).

In VanErtvelde the authors proposed code mutation (to generate application clones), a technique that mutates the original code of a real application to make harder/impossible reverse engineering. Their objective consists of allowing the distribution of those clones that have the same behaviour (in terms of performance) as the original. To test the results, they use the SPEC CPU2000 and MiBench benchmarks. They also provide a comparison between the different related works for code mutation, because the approaches differ in the way to preserve the proprietary application’s memory accesses and control flow behaviour. In these cases, the mutant code has the same execution time as the original application, which is one of the main objectives.

Clone morphing Wang2017 is different from Clone workloads. The first one proposes systematic changes to clone the behaviour of the application focusing on certain features. However, the second one tries to copy the application

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Figure 46: Jacobi I/O writing pattern while running concurrently with HACC-IO in shared nodes.

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Figure 47: Jacobi I/O writing pattern while running concurrently with HACC-IO in shared nodes.

Figure 48: I/O writing patterns related to the Jacobi I/O executions while running concurrently with HACC-IO in shared nodes.

Figure 49: HACC-IO - I/O time comparison between the interference produced by the original application and the clone per time step.

performance without providing real information about the original application. Therefore, clone morphing copies the cache/memory patterns for each application, and the clone workload tries to reproduce the performance loads. Their main contribution is the systematic method for producing new clones with performance behaviours that are the result of the combination of more than one application. The main weakness of this work is that the authors focus their

Figure 50: Jacobi IO - I/O time comparison between the interference produced by the original application and the clone per I/O phase.

work on the cache and memory patterns.

In Panda2017 the authors proposed PerfProx, another alternative to build clones based on real applications. However, this related work differs from other previous works because their clone generator tries to replicate the performance of the applications based on the performance counters (similar to our proposal), and it is only focused on database processes. PerfProx directly generates a general-purpose clone executable. They have evaluated their proposal on Cassandra, MongoDB and MySQL running both the data-serving and data-analysis on different platforms.

Regarding the I/O performance prediction in HPC platforms, the current state of the art confirms that storage I/O performance is hard to predict due to the potential and continuous interferences dorier2016damaris. One of the main causes of the I/O performance variability is the lack of scheduling algorithms for the I/O accesses to the storage hierarchy. For example, if two applications perform write operations at the same time, they can interfere, and the global performance and throughput will be affected.

There are a lot of related works on this topic, and they address the issues on different levels of the platform architecture. Many of them focus on the shared-burst buffers, which are an intermediate layer between the file system and the executing applications. They have been designed to manage the bursty I/O traffic efficiently. However, these shared-burst buffers can also suffer performance degradation due to I/O interference.

Several solutions like thapaliya2016managing, kougkas2016leveraging and tang2017toward have proposed mechanisms to mitigate the effect of the I/O interference based on coordinating the access to the shared-burst buffers and the parallel file systems.

Another different approach, Aequilibro newwirth2016using, provides I/O load balancing at file-system-level for mitigating the I/O interferences. son2017reducing introduces an approach in which the I/O accesses are analyzed at runtime to filter those accesses to the I/O nodes that have a low performance.

Other different points of view consists of predicting the application interferences alves2017multivariate and predicting the application I/O patterns snyder2015techniques dorier2015using for resource provisioning. These solutions

could be used to improve the accuracy of the I/O interference predictor used in our work. The idea consists of knowing in advance when two I/O accesses will take place to delay one of them, or even limit the I/O bandwidth for one application. In contrast to the previous works, the objective of this proposal is not to replicate the applications accurately. Instead, our goal is to reproduce the performance of the applications without extracting data from the binaries, without the necessity of dealing with code or data from the applications, and without a big penalty in terms of overhead. Moreover, the LIMITLESS' application clones are malleable using FlexMPI, which allows dynamic reconfiguration of the number of processes at runtime. Due to this, the system is able to analyze different configurations of the same application clone to discover its scalability and its impact on other applications (interference). This research line is relevant because more accurate clones will increase the accuracy of the predictors, the interference analysis and the scalability tests.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we introduce a new feature on LIMITLESS -a lightweight monitoring and scheduling framework designed to monitor and schedule applications- that consists of creating synthetic micro-benchmarks (also known as application clones) from the applications executed in the cluster. These clones reproduce the application behaviour and are based on the performance models produced by LIMITLESS, which captures and analyzes the application CPU, memory, communication and I/O patterns. In addition, the clones have malleable capabilities that permit to dynamically execute them with a changing number of processes and different data redistribution schemes.

One of the main characteristics of this proposal is that it uses the clones to enrich the application modelling, providing additional execution traces. These traces are used to train the networks and the machine learning algorithms without involving the real applications nor the platform users. Besides, clones do not contain proprietary information nor include any piece of code of the original application so they can be freely shared and used by other users or system components like the application and I/O schedulers in order to assert the optimization decisions that have been made.

In addition, the system uses different application clones to perform interference and scalability studies between applications, which allows the scheduler to share nodes between applications that do not cause interference. Note that, in case of performance degradation during the execution of real applications, the system will detect that situation, avoiding it by means of application migration or increasing or decreasing the processes using the malleability features.

In this work, we introduce the methodology for generating the application clones and evaluate its ability to reproduce the related application behaviour both considering the CPU and I/O perspectives. We also show how they can be effectively used to perform interference analysis in a more affordable way than using the actual applications. One future use of the application clones is the

replication of the I/O patterns produced by the applications, which also provides new possibilities for introducing more advanced I/O scheduling algorithms.

In future work, we plan to extend the algorithm to support GPU clones and provide more tests with real-world applications. Regarding the GPU cloning feature, the system monitor collects information from the GPU, but we do not model and replicate it yet.

References